

Development of combined attractiveness indicators

WP 4, Task 4.2-4.4, D.4.2

March 2024

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Project acronym	SPANDAM	
Project title	Modelo de evaluación de la dinámica demográfica en España (<i>Spanish Demographic Dynamics Assessment Model</i>)	
Project coordinator		
Project duration		
Deliverable No.	4.2	
Dissemination level	Confidential (CO) / Public (PU)	
Status		In progress
		Verified by other WP
	*	Final
Deliverable due date		
Date of delivery	08/03/2024	
Version	3.1	
Task team	4. Indicators	
Main beneficiary	SPANDAM	
Author(s)	Lidia Bonilla (USAL), Alberto del Rey (USAL), Amand Blanes (USAL)	

Date	Version	Contributors	Comments
13-09-2023	1.0	USAL, CED	General sections and first version of the indices
10-11-2023	2.0	USAL, CED	Second version of the indices based on the suggestions of the other project partners and the advisory committee
09-02-2024	3.0	USAL, CED	Third version of the indicators based on the requirements of the model and the suggestions of the other project partners
07-03-2024	3.1	USAL, UVa	Description of the methodology for the input variables after their introduction in the model

COPYRIGHT

Texto copyright.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT HISTORY	I
COPYRIGHT	II
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	III
LIST OF TABLES	IV
LIST OF FIGURES.....	IV
SUMMARY	VII
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
2. METHODOLOGY	2
2.1. SAMPLE.....	2
2.2. DATA.....	3
2.3. CALCULATION	4
3. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR THE POPULATION	7
3.1. COMPOSITION	7
3.2. VARIABLE DESCRIPTION.....	8
4. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR ECONOMIC ACTIVITY	51
4.1. COMPOSITION	51
4.2. VARIABLE DESCRIPTION.....	51
5. ATTRACTIVENESS INDICES FOR SPECIFIC TARGET GROUPS	68
5.1. COMPOSITION	68
5.2. WEIGHTINGS.....	69
CONCLUSIONS.....	72
REFERENCES.....	73

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Weightings of the dimensions in the specific attractiveness indices 69

Table 2. Composition of the specific attractiveness indices..... 69

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.1 of the index for the general population ..9

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.2 of the index for the general population 10

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.3 of the index for the general population 11

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.4 of the index for the general population 12

Figure 5. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.5 of the index for the general population 13

Figure 6. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.6 of the index for the general population 14

Figure 7. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.7 of the index for the general population 15

Figure 8. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.1 of the index for the general population 16

Figure 9. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.2 of the index for the general population 17

Figure 10. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.3 of the index for the general population 18

Figure 11. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.4 of the index for the general population 19

Figure 12. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.5 of the index for the general population 20

Figure 13. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.1 of the index for the general population 21

Figure 14. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.2 of the index for the general population 22

Figure 15. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.3 of the index for the general population 23

Figure 16. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.4 of the index for the general population 24

Figure 17. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.5 of the index for the general population 25

Figure 18. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.6 of the index for the general population 26

Figure 19. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.7 of the index for the general population 27

Figure 20. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.8 of the index for the general population 28

Figure 21. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.1 of the index for the general population 29

Figure 22. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.2 of the index for the general population 30

Figure 23. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.3 of the index for the general population 31

Figure 24. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.4 of the index for the general population 32

Figure 25. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.1 of the index for the general population 33

Figure 26. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.2 of the index for the general population 34

Figure 27. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.3 of the index for the general population 35

Figure 28. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.4 of the index for the general population 36

Figure 29. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.5 of the index for the general population 37

Figure 30. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.6 of the index for the general population 38

Figure 31. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.7 of the index for the general population 39

Figure 32. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.1 of the index for the general population 40

Figure 33. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.2 of the index for the general population 41

Figure 34. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.3 of the index for the general population 42

Figure 35. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.4 of the index for the general population 43

Figure 36. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.5 of the index for the general population 44

Figure 37. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.6 of the index for the general population 45

Figure 38. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.7 of the index for the general population 46

Figure 39. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.1 of the index for the general population 47

Figure 40. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.2 of the index for the general population 48

Figure 41. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.3 of the index for the general population 49

Figure 42. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.1 of the index for economic activity 52

Figure 43. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.2 of the index for economic activity 53

Figure 44. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.3 of the index for economic activity 54

Figure 45. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.4 of the index for economic activity 55

Figure 46. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.1 of the index for economic activity 56

Figure 47. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.2 of the index for economic activity 57

Figure 48. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.3 of the index for economic activity 58

Figure 49. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.4 of the index for economic activity 59

Figure 50. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.1 of the index for economic activity 60

Figure 51. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.2 of the index for economic activity 61

Figure 52. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.3 of the index for economic activity 62

Figure 53. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.4 of the index for economic activity 63

Figure 54. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.1 of the index for economic activity 64

Figure 55. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.2 of the index for economic activity 65

Figure 56. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.3 of the index for economic activity 66

Figure 57. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.4 of the index for economic activity 67

SUMMARY

This document presents the main methodological aspects that have marked the development of the aggregate indices introduced in the SPANDAM model. Five phases have been taken into account in the process of constructing the indices: definition of the study phenomenon (available in Deliverable 4.1), specification of the units of analysis, selection of the variables and dimensions, normalisation of the variables, and their aggregation. In this deliverable, the methodological aspects relating to the remaining four phases are presented in greater detail.

Regarding calculation, a total of five aggregated indices of territorial attractiveness have been constructed for the 8131 Spanish municipalities, each of them aimed at a different target audience: general population, young people, families, elderly people and companies. The first four share the same basic structure (7 dimensions) although they differ in the weight given to some variables and dimensions compared to others, while the fourth has its own specific structure (4 dimensions). All of them have been calculated using the adjusted Mazziotta-Pareto Index, which facilitates interpretation by working with scores ranging from 70 to 130, with 100 reflecting a reference value (the average of all municipalities).

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of benchmark indicators is key in the context of decision-making and policy analysis, as it allows monitoring phenomena, identifying trends, making comparisons and, above all, detecting which aspects should be addressed as a priority through public and private initiatives (OECD, 2008). With this in mind, the indicators are a fundamental part of the SPANDAM project, as they make it possible to understand the initial situation of the territories and to understand, through simulations, the magnitude of the effects that different policies can have on them. This is why one of the project's work packages is specifically aimed at selecting and constructing the indicators that will form part of the final SPANDAM tool.

In this framework, given that territorial attractiveness is a multidimensional concept that is not fully captured by any single variable, the need arises to build composite indices that summarise its different dimensions and components in an aggregated way. As already shown in the literature review presented in Deliverable 4.1, composite indices are used by a large number of territorial organisations to understand the situation of different territories with respect to a phenomenon (e.g. quality of life, competitiveness, etc.), as well as to analyse their evolution, compare them with each other, and use all this information to make more informed decisions.

On this basis, one of the objectives of the SPANDAM project is precisely to construct composite indices that allow us to measure the attractiveness of territories in a summarised way without having to explore different individual indicators one by one. An added difficulty we encounter in doing this is that, as already proven in Deliverable 4.1, territorial attractiveness is subjective, and can vary enormously depending on whether we want to attract companies or people, or even on the profile of the people we want to attract. Therefore, as opposed to the possibility of creating a single composite index of territorial attractiveness that could ignore these nuances, we have opted to construct different general and specific indices that allow us to more reliably approach the reality of each case. Specifically, a total of five aggregate indices have been constructed:

- Attractiveness index for the population
- Attractiveness index for economic activity
- Attractiveness index for the youth
- Attractiveness index for families
- Attractiveness index for the elderly

2. METHODOLOGY

As summarised by the Instituto Nacional de Estadística (2020), composite indices are based on the aggregation of different normalised variables with the final objective of obtaining a final score for each case. Therefore, we can summarise the construction phases of a composite index as follows:

1. Defining the study phenomenon
2. Specifying the units of analysis
3. Selecting the variables and the dimensions into which they are grouped
4. Normalising the variables
5. Aggregating the normalised variables

Given that phase 1 required a separate dedication due to the apparent lack of specificity of the concept of territorial attractiveness, an exhaustive analysis was previously dedicated to it, which can be consulted in Deliverable 4.1. The rest of the phases required to construct the composite indices included in the SPANDAM model are developed in greater detail below.

2.1. SAMPLE

To construct the different aggregate indices, the municipality has been chosen as the basic geographical unit, as it is the smallest territorial level for which exhaustive data are available. The use of municipal data has the advantage of making it possible to analyse relatively small portions of territory, while at the same time opening up the possibility of calculating supra-municipal indices through the aggregation of data. On the contrary, by using higher geographical levels (e.g. provinces) we could have access to a larger number of variables, but we would lose the possibility of exploring smaller territorial units (e.g. counties or municipalities), which are the focus of the project on depopulated areas. This leads us to opt for the first option.

Following this idea, we have included in the sample all those Spanish municipalities that were in vigour on 1 January 2023, which is equivalent to a total of 8,131 municipalities. It should be noted that during the processing of the data, a series of municipalities have been detected as 'problematic' on a statistical level, in that they present missing values in several of the variables considered. We can divide these municipalities into three groups according to the causality of their problems:

- Recently created municipalities: there are 8 municipalities that have been created in recent years, and which do not have values for data calculated prior to their creation date. The municipalities affected are the following:
 - Cerdedo-Cotobade (36902), created from the merger of the municipalities of Cerdedo and Cotobade in 2016.
 - San Martín del Tesorillo (11903), separated from the municipality of Jimena de la Frontera in 2018.
 - Fuente Carreteros (14901), separated from the municipality of Fuente Palmera in 2018.
 - La Guijarrosa (14902), separated from the municipality of Santaella in 2018.
 - Fornes (18077), separated from the municipality of Arenas del Rey in 2018.
 - Torrenueva Costa (18916), separated from the municipality of Motril in 2018.
 - La Zarza-Perrunal (21902), separated from the municipality of Calañas in 2018.
 - El Palmar de Troya (41904), separated from the municipality of Utrera in 2018.

- Municipalities located in exclaves: there are 3 municipalities that do not border with any other municipality belonging to the Spanish State, as they are located outside the general territorial limits:
 - Llívia (17094), enclave located in the French department of Pyrénées-Orientales.
 - Ceuta (51001), autonomous city located on the coast of Morocco.
 - Melilla (52001), autonomous city located on the coast of Morocco.
- Island municipalities: there are a total of 155 municipalities located on the 11 main islands of Spain, from which municipalities located on the mainland or on other islands are not accessible by land. This is problematic in some cases, as certain indicators, such as access time to a train station or motorway/highway, give indeterminate values for municipalities located in island without such infrastructure.

All cases of variables in which missing values have been identified for some municipalities have been resolved by applying different methodologies depending on the reason for the incidence and the nature of the indicator. For more detailed information on the procedures carried out in each case, please consult the variable sheets presented in this document.

2.2. DATA

As defined in the literature, a composite index is nothing more than a mathematical combination of individual variables that reflect different components of the same multidimensional phenomenon (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2018). Therefore, the next step in creating a composite index, after defining the phenomenon to be analysed and determining the desired level of geographical disaggregation, is to select those variables that will be used to construct it.

However, it is important to stress that we cannot include just any variable in the index, since the variables selected must meet two basic requirements: on the one hand, as is obvious, they must be related to the phenomenon we are trying to measure, be it territorial attractiveness for the general population, for businesses, for youth, etc.; and on the other hand, the variables must have data available for all the municipalities, or, if there are missing data, they must be few in number and must be reliably imputable.

Bearing the latter in mind, the main barrier we have encountered when constructing the different indices is precisely related to the scarcity of disaggregated data at the municipal level available for all the territories. In this sense, it has often been observed that some municipal variables of interest are available for some geographical regions but not for others, or that the values of municipalities with small sizes are not made public for reasons of statistical confidentiality. For this reason, we have found that some very relevant aspects of territorial attractiveness, identified in various studies, do not have data with which to measure them.

In order to solve this limitation, and to avoid that some important aspects are left out of the model due to the lack of data, we have finally decided to consider two types of variables:

- Base variables: these are variables extracted from secondary sources, such as the National Statistics Institute (INE) or the Centre for Demographic Studies (CED), for which data is available for all municipalities. Within this group we can broadly distinguish three groups of variables:
 - Simple: these are those variables that have not been subjected to any calculations beyond basic statistical procedures (e.g., proportions, averages, etc.), preserving the structure of the source from which they have been extracted.

- Rates: these are variables that have been calculated by dividing the original data by the size of the population to obtain a proportion. They are generally presented in the format 'X per 100 or 1000 inhabitants/enterprises/etc.'
- Access time: these are variables that reflect the approximate distance by road to a given service, using presence/absence data matrices as a reference. These variables have been calculated from a table of distances between municipalities extracted from the Google Maps service, in which the approximate distance in minutes of driving between the centroids of each pair of municipalities is represented. Thus, when a municipality has the service in question, it is assigned a 0 (the best possible value), and when it does not, the value corresponding to the shortest distance to a municipality that does have it is imputed.
- Input variables: these are variables that, as they cannot be incorporated from the pre-existing databases, will be introduced by the users of the SPANDAM tool themselves based on their knowledge and perceptions. The introduction of this second type of variables into the model is based on the assumption that the users of the tool are knowledgeable about the territories they want to evaluate, and that they will therefore be able to assess the situation of these territories in terms of different aspects (e.g. quality of life, availability of housing, etc.) using scales. However, this type of variable requires specific treatment, since, as they are not available for more territories, they cannot be normalised like the rest of the variables, nor can they be used to make comparisons between territories.

In sections 3 and 4 of this document, the basic descriptive, technical and methodological aspects of each of the variables that make up the different composite territorial attractiveness indices can be consulted in detail.

2.3. CALCULATION

In order to construct the different attractiveness indices, we have chosen to use a widely used method, which is the one developed by Mazziotta and Pareto in its adjusted version: the Adjusted Mazziotta-Pareto Index (abbreviated as AMPI). Although there are many methods that allow the construction of aggregate indices, the AMPI has been selected among all of them because it is a robust method whose calculation is simple and transparent, which provides easily interpretable results, and which also allows comparisons between territories and/or periods (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2018). Proof of its good performance is that the National Statistics Institute itself uses it to calculate its Multidimensional Quality of Life Indicator (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2020).

The construction of the aggregate indices through the AMPI method requires the application of two successive phases: firstly, the normalisation of the variables; and, subsequently, the aggregation of the variables and dimensions. In any case, it is important to stress that AMPI can only be applied for what we have called base variables, since in order to carry out the normalisation process it is necessary to know the distribution of the values of all the territories in the variable. Therefore, as the input variables will only have known values for a single territory (the subject of the analysis), they cannot be included directly in the AMPI calculations, but require subsequent incorporation.

2.3.1. NORMALISATION

When we have a large set of variables, it is very common for them to have completely different units of measurement and scales, so it is not possible to aggregate them without first making them comparable. Therefore, an essential step in the construction of composite indices is to transform the variables to obtain dimensionless data so that they all share the same standard and can be aggregated effectively. Moreover, such a normalisation process allows determining the sense of the relationships between the individual variables and the phenomenon to be measured, inverting the scale in cases where the relationship is negative so that the aggregation makes sense (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2016).

Specifically, normalisation in AMPI is based on rescaling the values with respect to two reference points: a minimum value (Min_{x_j}) and a maximum value (Max_{x_j}), which will define the range of possible values (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2018). By operating in this way, we obtain for each variable a normalised version in which the scores oscillate approximately between the values 70 and 130:

Given a matrix $X = \{x_{ij}\}$, we calculate the normalised matrix $R = \{r_{ij}\}$ as follows::

$$R_{ij} = \frac{(x_{ij} - Min_{x_j})}{(Max_{x_j} - Min_{x_j})} 60 + 70$$

In case variable j has a negative polarity (when its relationship with territorial attractiveness is inverse), the complement of (1) with respect to 200 is calculated (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2018).

To facilitate the interpretation of the results, the reference points (Min_{x_j} and Max_{x_j}) can be set in such a way that a value of 100 in the normalised variable represents a reference value, which in our case is the average of the territories. This means that territories scoring below 100 will have a lower relative position than the average, and those scoring above 100 will have a higher relative position. Moreover, the closer a territory's score is to any of the extremes, the further away it will be from the average, both for the better (if it is close to 130) and for the worse (if it is close to 70). Following this idea, we estimate the reference points Min_{x_j} and Max_{x_j} through the following formula, where M_{x_j} represents the average of the variable, and Inf_{x_j} and Sup_{x_j} represent the minimum and maximum values of the distribution respectively:

$$\begin{cases} Min_{x_j} = M_{x_j} - \left(\frac{Sup_{x_j} - Inf_{x_j}}{2} \right) \\ Max_{x_j} = M_{x_j} + \left(\frac{Sup_{x_j} - Inf_{x_j}}{2} \right) \end{cases}$$

In any case, before normalising the variables following the AMPI method, some of them had to be subjected to a process of imputation of extreme cases to correct exaggerated asymmetries, since the presence of extreme municipalities in the sample often causes distortions in the distributions. The imputation method selected has been known as capping, using the values of certain percentiles (lower and/or higher depending on the relative position of the outliers) to replace the extreme values that distort the distribution.

2.3.2. AGGREGATION

Since territorial attractiveness is a multidimensional phenomenon, the variables are aggregated in two successive steps: first, variables belonging to the same dimension are aggregated together, and finally the dimensions are aggregated to obtain an overall index. Therefore, for each index we will obtain, on the one hand, a series of sub-indexes that represent each of the dimensions considered, and, on the other hand, a global index that summarises the whole phenomenon. In any case, the aggregation method is the same in both phases, following the AMPI guidelines.

Specifically, the AMPI method is based on a linear aggregation of the standardised variables through the calculation of the arithmetic average of the values, to which a penalty factor is subsequently added. This factor aims to take into account the variability of the results within each unit of analysis, penalising those with less balanced scores on the variables (Mazziotta & Pareto, 2018). Thus, the generalised form of the AMPI is summarised in the following formula, where M_{ri} , S_{ri} and cv_{ri} denote the mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of unit i respectively:

$$AMPI_i^{+/-} = M_{ri} \pm S_{ri} \cdot cv_{ri}$$

When the index is positive, in that high values in the index correspond to positive variations of the phenomenon, as in our case, the $AMPI^-$ version is used. On the other hand, when the index is negative, we use the $AMPI^+$ version.

It should be noted in this regard that the average used by default in the aggregation of the variables has been the arithmetic one, so that all the variables that make up the same dimension obtain the same weight in all cases. The type of average used in the aggregation of the dimensions, however, varies according to the index: the first two use the arithmetic average, while in the three specific indexes different weights have been used to weight the dimensions differently according to the characteristics of the population group to which they are addressed.

2.3.3. INCORPORATION OF INPUT VARIABLES

To introduce the input variables into the SPANDAM tool model, an ad-hoc method has been designed in which three clearly differentiated phases can be distinguished:

1. Introduction of the values by the user: the tool interface shows the user the question corresponding to the variable in question, allowing him to rate his answer on a scale from 0 to 10. The user can decide not to add any answer, in which case the variable will not be taken into account and therefore the following phases will not be applicable.
2. Transformation of the values: the user's response, whose value will be between 0 and 10 (including these), is transformed through an internal normalisation procedure so that it shares scale with the normalised base variables. In this way, a value between 70 and 130 is obtained, where 0 will correspond to the minimum and 10 to the maximum.
3. Aggregation of the values: the normalised value is added to the score of the corresponding dimension using a weighted average. The weight used in the aggregation may vary according to the user's preferences, although a weighting that is equivalent to the unit weight that each of the base variables has in the dimension may be pre-established, so that it counts as one more variable in the computation. In either case, the final value will preserve the scale of scores between 70 and 130 so that comparability is not lost.

3. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR THE POPULATION

The objective of this index is to measure the level of attractiveness of Spanish territories when it comes to attracting and retaining population. It should be noted that this index does not distinguish between the type of population that is attracted and/or retained (which is reserved for the specific indices presented in section 5), but rather seeks to reflect population attractiveness in general.

3.1. COMPOSITION

The Attractiveness Index for the Population is constructed on the basis of a total of 50 variables (41 base and 9 input) collected in 7 dimensions, which, as we have already mentioned, in turn function as sub-indices. The precise composition of the index is presented below (input variables are marked with an asterisk):

1. Demography: refers to the composition of the population and the population dynamics of the territories. It is made up of 7 variables:
 - 1.1. Population density
 - 1.2. Average age
 - 1.3. Presence of women
 - 1.4. Population growth
 - 1.5. Births
 - 1.6. Migratory dynamics
 - 1.7. New residents
2. Economy: refers to the economic structure of the territories, taking into account their business environment, their labor market and the purchasing power of their residents. It is composed of 6 variables:
 - 2.1. Business presence
 - 2.2. Economic diversification
 - 2.3. Income
 - 2.4. Unemployment
 - 2.5. Temporariness
 - 2.6. Housing availability*
3. General services: refers to the availability or proximity of services of relevance to the population, such as cultural resources, banking services or companies dedicated to the provision of services for individuals. It is calculated from the aggregation of 10 variables:
 - 3.1. Bank office
 - 3.2. Post office
 - 3.3. Library
 - 3.4. Police station
 - 3.5. Bar
 - 3.6. Day care centre
 - 3.7. Entertainment
 - 3.8. Daily services
 - 3.9. Institutional quality*
 - 3.10. Social capital*

4. Health services: refers to the availability of services related to health care in the territory or its surroundings. It is made up of 5 variables:
 - 4.1. Pharmacy
 - 4.2. Health centre
 - 4.3. Hospital
 - 4.4. Emergency services
 - 4.5. Quality of healthcare*
5. Educational services: this refers to the availability of different types of training centers in the territory or its surroundings, corresponding to each of the educational stages. It is made up of a total of 8 variables:
 - 5.1. Childcare
 - 5.2. Pre-school and Primary Education
 - 5.3. Compulsory Secondary Education
 - 5.4. Baccalaureate and Vocational Training
 - 5.5. University Education
 - 5.6. Extracurricular activities
 - 5.7. Extracurricular training
 - 5.8. Work-family conciliation*
6. Communications: this refers to the ease with which the residents of the territory communicate with the rest, either physically (by public transport or their own vehicle) or telematically (through the Internet). It is made up of 8 variables:
 - 6.1. Distance to the provincial capital
 - 6.2. Distance to a reference municipality
 - 6.3. High-capacity road
 - 6.4. Petrol station
 - 6.5. Railway station
 - 6.6. Taxi
 - 6.7. Internet coverage
 - 6.8. Quality of public transport service*
7. Environment: refers to environmental aspects that characterise the territories and influence other dimensions (economic structure, accessibility, availability of services, etc.). It is made up of 6 variables, half of them of the input type:
 - 7.1. Relief
 - 7.2. Rainfall
 - 7.3. Temperature
 - 7.4. Landscape and heritage attractiveness*
 - 7.5. Water quality*
 - 7.6. Air quality*

3.2. VARIABLE DESCRIPTION

Given that the variables that make up this index come from various data sources and are of different natures, a detailed description of each of them is presented below, including specifications such as: the form in which they are measured; the sources from which they have been extracted; the period to which they refer; their relationship (direct or inverse) with population attractiveness; the possible imputations that may have been made in the calculations; and the reference values used in their normalisation. Details of the input variables are shown in a separate section (3.2.8).

3.2.1. DIMENSION 1: DEMOGRAPHY

VARIABLE 1.1: POPULATION DENSITY

INDICATOR: Population Density

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE); Explorador Social (CED)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of inhabitants the municipality has per square kilometre of its surface area.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more population the municipality has, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 inhab/km²

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 179.3 inhab/km²

VALUE 130: ≥ 359.6 inhab/km²

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.2: AVERAGE AGE

INDICATOR: Average age

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average age of the population residing in the territory.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the older the population of the municipality, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 61.8 years

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 50.4 years

VALUE 130: ≤ 39 years

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.3: PRESENCE OF WOMEN

INDICATOR: Masculinity index

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of men for every 100 women residing in the municipality.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the more male-dominated the population of the municipality, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 1 (45080 – Illán de Vacas) because there are no women living in the municipality and therefore it is not possible to make the calculation. To solve the problem, the municipality concerned has been assigned the maximum value of the distribution.

VALUE 70: ≥ 146.7 men

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 116.5 men

VALUE 130: ≤ 86.4 men

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.4: POPULATION GROWTH

INDICATOR: Population Growth Rate

PERIOD: 2016-2020

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average annual growth experienced by the population size of the municipality in the period per thousand inhabitants.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more the population of the municipality has increased, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 17 municipalities show problems in this indicator because they have undergone territorial reconfigurations since 2016. To solve this problem, those municipalities that were merged at some point in the period have been computed as a single municipality, and the resulting rate has been imputed to both.

VALUE 70: ≤ -55.4

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): -6.1

VALUE 130: ≥ 43.2

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.4 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.5: BIRTHS**INDICATOR:** Birth Rate**PERIOD:** 2016-2020**SOURCE:** Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics**DESCRIPTION:** It measures the average number of births occurring annually in the municipality per thousand inhabitants.**RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS:** Direct; the more births occur in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.**MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES:** 0**VALUE 70:** 0 births**VALUE 100 (AVERAGE):** 5.1 births**VALUE 130:** ≥ 10.1 births

Figure 5. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.5 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.6: MIGRATION DYNAMICS**INDICATOR:** Migration Growth Rate**PERIOD:** 2016-2020**SOURCE:** Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics**DESCRIPTION:** It measures the average annual population gains (or losses) of the municipality derived from migratory movements per thousand inhabitants.**RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS:** Direct; the more inhabitants the municipality gains, the more attractive it will be.**MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES:** 0**VALUE 70:** ≤ -35.4 **VALUE 100 (AVERAGE):** 3.7**VALUE 130:** ≥ 42.7

Figure 6. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.6 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 1.7: NEW RESIDENTS

INDICATOR: Percentage of population settled in the municipality in the last 5 years

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the proportion of inhabitants of the municipality who came to live there in any of the previous 5 years.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more newcomers to the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 7 municipalities show problems in this indicator due to the fact that they were created only three years before the reference year, so originally their value in the variable reaches 100%. To solve this problem, the percentage of residents arriving in the affected municipalities from the year after their creation, i.e. in the years 2019 and 2020, has been estimated.

VALUE 70: $\leq 3\%$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 15.5%

VALUE 130: $\geq 28\%$

Figure 7. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.7 of the index for the general population

3.2.2. DIMENSION 2: ECONOMY

VARIABLE 2.1: BUSINESS PRESENCE

INDICATOR: Number of enterprises registered in the municipality

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of physical and legal companies, including branches, located in the municipality.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more companies located in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 companies

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 502 companies

VALUE 130: ≥ 1004 companies

Figure 8. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 2.2: ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION

INDICATOR: Shannon Economic Diversification Index

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España)

DESCRIPTION: It measures how diversified the economy of the municipality is in terms of the distribution of companies in the 88 divisions of the National Classification of Economic Activities (CNAE-2009).

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more diverse the activities of companies in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≤ 1.5

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 3.2

VALUE 130: ≥ 4.9

Figure 9. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 2.3: INCOME

INDICATOR: Average net income per person

PERIOD: 2020

SOURCE: Atlas de distribución de renta de los hogares (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the net income received on average by the inhabitants of the municipality on an annual basis.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more income people living in the municipality receive, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 8 municipalities (04026, 06032, 13095, 21027, 39051, 39088, 46201 and 46226) do not show the data for reasons of confidentiality. In these cases the provincial average value has been imputed.

VALUE 70: $\leq 8,539$ euros

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 12,891 euros

VALUE 130: $\geq 17,243$ euros

Figure 10. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 2.4: UNEMPLOYMENT

INDICATOR: Unemployment rate

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the percentage of unemployed people out of the total number of active people living in the municipality.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the more inhabitants of the municipality are unemployed, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: $\geq 25\%$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 14.7%

VALUE 130: $\leq 4.4\%$

Figure 11. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.4 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 2.5: TEMPORARINESS

INDICATOR: Temporariness rate

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the percentage of employed persons living in the municipality with temporary contracts.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the more workers resident in the municipality have temporary contracts, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: $\geq 51.6\%$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 28.7%

VALUE 130: $\leq 5.8\%$

Figure 12. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.5 of the index for the general population

3.2.3. DIMENSION 3: GENERAL SERVICES

VARIABLE 3.1: BANK OFFICE

INDICATOR: Access time to a bank office

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Registro de oficinas de entidades supervisadas (Banco de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to get to the nearest municipality with a bank branch.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a bank branch, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 14 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 7 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 13. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.2: POST OFFICE

INDICATOR: Access time to a post office

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Base de datos de puntos de entrega (Correos); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a post office.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a post office, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 28.6 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 14.3 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 14. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.3: LIBRARY

INDICATOR: Access time to a public library

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Directorio de bibliotecas españolas (Ministerio de Cultura); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a public library.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: nverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a public library, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 18.2 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 9.1 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 15. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.4: POLICE STATION

INDICATOR: Access time to a police station of the state or autonomous regions' security forces and bodies

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to get to the nearest municipality with a police station.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a police station, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 21.8 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 10.9 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 16. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.4 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.5: BAR**INDICATOR:** Absence of bar**PERIOD:** 2023**SOURCE:** Report *La dimensión social de la hostelería* (Asociación de directoras y gerentes de servicios sociales de España)**DESCRIPTION:** It measures whether the municipality lacks a bar-type establishment.**RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS:** Inversa; Inverse; if there is no bar in the municipality, it will be less attractive.**MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES:** In order to avoid overestimation of the 6703 municipalities that have a bar, they have been imputed the average normalised value that they have in the other variables that make up the general services dimension.**VALUE 70:** No bar

Figure 17. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.5 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.6: DAY CARE CENTRE

INDICATOR: Access time to a day centre for the elderly

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Envejecimiento en Red (CSIC); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a day centre for the elderly.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a day centre, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: The island of La Gomera does not have any day centre in its territory, so the six municipalities located there have been imputed the highest value of the distribution.

VALUE 70: ≥ 30 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 15 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 18. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.6 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.7: ENTERTAINMENT

INDICATOR: Access time to a company providing entertainment services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with an entertainment company, such as cinemas, theatres and the like. To determine which companies fall into this group, the corresponding CNAE-2009 codes have been considered.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes for the inhabitants of the municipality to go to an entertainment business, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 37.2 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 18.6 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 19. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.7 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 3.8: DAILY SERVICES

INDICATOR: Ratio of enterprises offering services to individuals per thousand inhabitants

PERIOD: 2023 (base poblacional de 2021)

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España)

DESCRIPTION: Measures the number of businesses registered in the municipality that offer services to individuals (e.g. hairdressers, food shops, etc.) per thousand residents. To determine which enterprises fall into this group, the corresponding CNAE-2009 codes have been considered.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more businesses offering services to the population there are in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 companies

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 20.1 companies

VALUE 130: ≥ 40.2 companies

Figure 20. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.8 of the index for the general population

3.2.4. DIMENSION 4: HEALTH SERVICES

VARIABLE 4.1: PHARMACY

INDICATOR: Access time to a pharmacy office

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Infraestructura de datos espaciales (MITECO); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a pharmacy.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a pharmacy, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 7 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 3.5 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 21. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 4.2: HEALTH CENTRE

INDICATOR: Access time to a health centre (Centro de Salud)

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Catálogo de centros de Atención Primaria del Sistema Nacional de Salud (Ministerio de Sanidad); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: Measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a health centre.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a health centre, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 23 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 11.5 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 22. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 4.3: HOSPITAL

INDICATOR: Access time to a hospital

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Catálogo Nacional de Hospitales (Ministerio de Sanidad); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: Measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to get to the nearest municipality with a hospital.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a hospital, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 68.2 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 34.1 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 23. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 4.4: EMERGENCY SERVICES

INDICATOR: Access time to a health facility with emergency services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Catálogo de Centros de Atención Urgente Extrahospitalaria (Ministerio de Sanidad); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a hospital.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to an emergency centre, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 31 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 15.5 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 24. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.4 of the index for the general population

3.2.5. DIMENSION 5: EDUCATIONAL SERVICES

VARIABLE 5.1: CHILDCARE

INDICATOR: Access time to a company offering childcare services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a child day care company.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a childcare centre, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 43.4 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 21.7 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 25. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.2: PRE-SCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION

INDICATOR: Access time to a centre offering pre-school and/or primary school education

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Registro estatal de centros docentes no universitarios (Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a school that provides pre-school and/or primary education.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to an Infant and/or Primary school, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 12 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 6 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 26. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.3: COMPULSORY SECONDARY EDUCATION

INDICATOR: Access time to a centre offering compulsory secondary education (ESO)

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Registro estatal de centros docentes no universitarios (Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to get to the nearest municipality with a school providing compulsory secondary education.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a secondary school, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 24.4 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 12.2 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 27. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.4: BACCALAUREATE AND VOCATIONAL TRAINING

INDICATOR: Access time to a centre offering Baccaulaureate and/or Vocational Training courses

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Registro estatal de centros docentes no universitarios (Ministerio de Educación, Formación Profesional y Deportes); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality that has a centre offering Baccaulaureate and/or Vocational Training.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a post-compulsory secondary school, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 30.4 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 15.2 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 28. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.4 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.5: UNIVERSITY STUDIES

INDICATOR: Access time to a public university institution

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Official websites of Spanish public universities; Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to get to the nearest municipality with a public university centre.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a public university centre, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≤ 91.2 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 45.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 29. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.5 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.6: EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

INDICATOR: Access time to a company offering cultural, recreational and/or sport education services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a company offering cultural, recreational and/or sports education services.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes for the inhabitants of the municipality to go to such a service, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 57.6 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 28.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 30. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.6 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 5.7: EXTRACURRICULAR TRAINING

INDICATOR: Access time to a company offering other types of training

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to go to the nearest municipality with a company dedicated to extracurricular education (language schools, revision, etc.).

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a company of this type, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 21.6 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 10.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 31. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 5.7 of the index for the general population

3.2.6. DIMENSION 6: COMMUNICATIONS

VARIABLE 6.1: DISTANCE TO THE PROVINCIAL CAPITAL

INDICATOR: Access time to the provincial capital

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the capital of the province in which the municipality is located.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to get to the capital of their province, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 58 municipalities initially lack data because they are island municipalities situated on islands where the respective provincial capitals are not located. In these cases, it has been interpreted that the impossibility of accessing the capital by road is very negative, so the maximum value of the distribution has been imputed to them.

VALUE 70: ≥ 97.1 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 53 minutes

VALUE 130: ≤ 8.9 minutes

Figure 32. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.2: DISTANCE TO A REFERENCE MUNICIPALITY

INDICATOR: Access time to a municipality with more than 2,000 inhabitants

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the nearest municipality with at least 2,000 inhabitants.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a municipality of that size, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 31 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 15.5 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 33. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.3: HIGH CAPACITY ROAD

INDICATOR: Access time to motorway or dual carriageway

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to access the nearest motorway or dual carriageway.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to reach a high capacity road, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 47 municipalities initially lack this data: 44 are located on islands that have no motorways or dual carriageways and the remaining 3 are exclaves. In the case of Llivia, as it is an exclave that can be accessed by land, the value relative to the nearest municipality (Puigcerdà) has been taken and the approximate distance between the two municipalities has been added. In the rest of the cases, the impossibility of accessing a high-capacity road is interpreted as something very negative, so the maximum value of the distribution has been imputed.

VALUE 70: ≥ 35.6 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 17.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 34. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.3 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.4: PETROL STATION

INDICATOR: Access time to a petrol station

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Sistema de Información Geográfica Nacional (IGN); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the nearest municipality with a petrol station.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a petrol station, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 17 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 8.5 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 35. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.4 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.5: RAILWAY STATION

INDICATOR: Access time to a train station

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the nearest municipality with a train station.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to get to a train station, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 104 municipalities initially lack data because they are island municipalities and autonomous cities where there is no railway structure. In these cases, it has been interpreted that the impossibility of accessing a railway station by road is very negative, so the maximum value of the distribution has been imputed to them.

VALUE 70: ≥ 55.6 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 27.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 36. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.5 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.6: TAXI

INDICATOR: Access time to taxi services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the nearest municipality with a taxi service.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes the inhabitants of the municipality to go to a municipality with a taxi service, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 19.4 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 9.7 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 37. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.6 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 6.7: INTERNET COVERAGE

INDICATOR: Percentage of population with internet coverage of 100 mbps

PERIOD: 2020

SOURCE: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico

DESCRIPTION: It measures the percentage of inhabitants of the municipality that have internet access with a connection speed of at least 100 megabits per second.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more inhabitants of the municipality have access to a fast internet connection, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0%

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 37.5%

VALUE 130: $\geq 75\%$

Figure 38. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 6.7 of the index for the general population

3.2.7. DIMENSION 7: ENVIRONMENT

VARIABLE 7.1: RELIEF

INDICATOR: Average slope

PERIOD: 2018

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average slope of the terrain within the boundaries of the municipality.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the steeper the terrain, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: The 7 municipalities that have been formed as of 2018 have missing values in this variable. They have been imputed the value relative to the municipality they were part of before their segregation.

VALUE 70: $\geq 25.1\%$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 13.4%

VALUE 130: $\leq 1.6\%$

Figure 39. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.1 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 7.2: RAINFALL

INDICATOR: Annual cumulative rainfall

PERIOD: 1980-2010

SOURCE: Agencia Estatal de Meteorología; Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average amount of litres per square metre accumulated from the rainfall recorded annually in the municipality between 1980 and 2010.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more natural water the municipality receives, the more attractive it is.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 20 municipalities have missing values in this variable: 7 that were created after 2018, to which the value relative to the municipality to which they belonged before that date has been imputed; 11 that have areas of less than 2 km², to which the average value of the neighbouring municipalities has been imputed; and the two autonomous cities, which have been assigned the data extracted from Climate-Data.org, which refers to the period 1991-2021.

VALUE 70: ≤ 110.6 litres/m²

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 657.7 litres/m²

VALUE 130: ≥ 1204.9 litres/m²

Figure 40. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.2 of the index for the general population

VARIABLE 7.3: TEMPERATURE

INDICATOR: Average annual temperature

PERIOD: 1980-2010

SOURCE: Agencia Estatal de Meteorología; Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average annual temperature in degrees Celsius recorded in the municipality between 1980 and 2010.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the higher the average temperature recorded throughout the year in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 20 municipalities have missing values in this variable: 7 that were created after 2018, to which the value relative to the municipality to which they belonged before that date has been imputed; 11 that have areas of less than 2 km², to which the average value of the neighbouring municipalities has been imputed; and the two autonomous cities, which have been assigned the data extracted from Climate-Data.org, which refers to the period 1991-2021.

VALUE 70: $\leq 8.2^{\circ}\text{C}$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 13.4°C

VALUE 130: $\geq 18.5^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 41. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 7.3 of the index for the general population

3.2.8. INPUT VARIABLES

VARIABLE 2.6: HOUSING AVAILABILITY

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which there is available housing that can be used by potential new residents in the territory, as well as its condition and affordability.

VARIABLE 3.9: INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which the institutions in charge of managing the territory's development strategies promote or facilitate the development of initiatives or projects of interest to the population.

VARIABLE 3.10: SOCIAL CAPITAL

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which support networks exist among residents and whether they join together to promote things for the territory.

VARIABLE 4.5: HEALTH CARE

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which health care (primary, specialised, etc.) is adequate, taking into account issues such as quality of care and waiting times.

VARIABLE 5.8: WORK-FAMILY CONCILIATION

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which the population with dependent minors has access to adequate conciliation services (e.g. educational centres, school canteens, extracurricular activities, informal support, etc.) to help them organise their work and personal life.

VARIABLE 6.8: QUALITY OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT SERVICE

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which the population without private vehicles can move easily around the territory and its surroundings, taking into account the availability, frequency, price, convenience, etc. of public transport.

VARIABLE 7.4: LANDSCAPE AND HERITAGE ATTRACTIVENESS

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which the natural (protected areas, natural parks, etc.) and cultural (monuments, architecture, etc.) landscape of the territory and its surroundings are attractive to residents and visitors.

VARIABLE 7.5: WATER QUALITY

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which domestic water is suitable for consumption, taking into account its potability, taste, hardness, cleanliness, etc.

VARIABLE 7.6: AIR QUALITY

DESCRIPTION: It assesses the extent to which there is atmospheric pollution in the environment and the seriousness of its implications for the resident population.

4. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

The aim of this index is to measure the level of attractiveness of Spanish territories when it comes to attracting, promoting and retaining economic activity in the form of companies. The index tries to capture some of the most relevant aspects that may affect the location decision of companies in general, taking into account the scarce availability of adequate data.

4.1. COMPOSITION

The Business Attractiveness Index is constructed on the basis of 4 dimensions, each of which is composed of 4 variables. Although this index shares some variables with the population index, most of them are specifically designed from a business point of view. The precise composition of the index is presented below:

1. Human capital: this refers to the availability and quality of workforce in the territory and its environment. The 4 variables that make up this dimension are as follows:
 - 1.1. Economically active population
 - 1.2. Workers
 - 1.3. Education
 - 1.4. Population growth
2. Exposure: this refers to the presence of potential clients in the territory. It is constructed from the following variables:
 - 2.1. Residents
 - 2.2. Likelihood of being visited
 - 2.3. National visitors
 - 2.4. International visitors
3. Accessibility: this refers to the existence of adequate connections with other territories, both spatially and digitally. It is calculated by aggregating these 4 variables:
 - 3.1. High capacity roads
 - 3.2. Transport and storage
 - 3.3. Distance to an urban municipality
 - 3.4. Internet coverage
4. Business dynamism: this refers to the presence and diversity of economic activity in the territory. It is made up of the 4 variables shown below:
 - 4.1. Presence of companies
 - 4.2. Evolution of the number of companies
 - 4.3. Economic diversification
 - 4.4. Services to companies

4.2. VARIABLE DESCRIPTION

As with the previous index, the detail of the 16 variables that make up the index for economic activity is shown below, with their respective data: source, period, ratio, imputations, normalisation, etc.

4.2.1. DIMENSION 1: HUMAN CAPITAL

VARIABLE 1.1: ECONOMICALLY ACTIVE POPULATION

INDICATOR: Labour force participation rate

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of residents of the municipality who are in an economically active situation.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more economically active population in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≤ 2 inhabitants

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 2,768 inhabitants

VALUE 130: $\geq 5,534$ inhabitants

Figure 42. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.1 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 1.2: WORKERS

INDICATOR: People with its workplace located in the municipality

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Estadísticas de Afiliación y alta de Trabajadores (Seguridad Social)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average number of workers whose place of work is located in the municipality throughout the year, regardless of whether they live there or not.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more people working in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: In cases where the number of contributors in a category of workers is greater than 0 but less than 5, the data is not shown for reasons of statistical confidentiality. In such cases the intermediate value (2.5) has been imputed.

VALUE 70: 0 workers

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 2,494 workers

VALUE 130: $\geq 4,990$ workers

Figure 43. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.2 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 1.3: EDUCATION

INDICATOR: Percentage of population aged 16-64 with university education and/or vocational training studies

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the proportion of working-age residents with vocational and/or university qualifications.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more educated the population of the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: $\leq 18.2\%$

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 44.5%

VALUE 130: $\geq 70.8\%$

Figure 44. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.3 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 1.4: POPULATION GROWTH

INDICATOR: Population Growth Rate

PERIOD: 2016-2020

SOURCE: Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the growth experienced by the population size of the municipality in the period

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more the population of the municipality has grown, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 17 municipalities show problems in this indicator because they have undergone territorial reconfigurations since 2016. To solve this problem, those municipalities that were merged at some point in the period have been computed as a single municipality, and the resulting rate has been imputed to both.

VALUE 70: ≤ -55.4

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): -6.1

VALUE 130: ≥ 43.2

Figure 45. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 1.4 of the index for economic activity

4.2.2. DIMENSION 2: EXPOSURE

VARIABLE 2.1: RESIDENTS

INDICATOR: Census population

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of people residing in the municipality according to the census.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more people living in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 inhabitants

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 5,830 inhabitants

VALUE 130: $\geq 11,662$ inhabitants

Figure 46. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.1 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 2.2: PROBABILITY OF BEING VISITED

INDICATOR: Number of services present in the municipality

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Censo de Población y Viviendas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the number of services present in the municipality out of a total of 35 selected services (administrative offices, shops, educational centres, health centres, etc.).

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more services there are in the municipality, the more likely it is that people will visit it, and therefore the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 services

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 9,5 services

VALUE 130: ≥ 19 services

Figure 47. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.2 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 2.3: NATIONAL VISITORS

INDICATOR: Number of annual visits from other provinces

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Medición del turismo a partir de teléfonos móviles (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate number of visits from people living in other provinces of the country that the municipality received over the period.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more external visits the municipality receives, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 3,784 municipalities received less than 30 interprovincial visits in at least one of the 12 months of the year, so the INE, for reasons of statistical confidentiality, does not provide the exact number of visits in the months concerned. To solve this problem, the average value of the possible values (14.5) has been imputed for those months without data.

VALUE 70: 174 visits

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 14,353 visits

VALUE 130: $\geq 28,538$ visits

Figure 48. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.3 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 2.4: INTERNATIONAL VISITORS

INDICATOR: Number of annual visits from other countries

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Medición del turismo a partir de teléfonos móviles (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate number of visits the municipality from people living abroad to over the period.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more external visits the municipality receives, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 5,064 municipalities received less than 30 international visits in at least one of the 12 months of the year, so the INE, for reasons of statistical confidentiality, does not provide the exact number of visits in the months concerned. To solve this problem, the average value of the possible values (14.5) has been imputed for those months without data.

VALUE 70: 146 visits

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 33,147 visits

VALUE 130: $\geq 66,147$ visits

Figure 49. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 2.4 of the index for economic activity

4.2.3. DIMENSION 3: ACCESSIBILITY

VARIABLE 3.1: HIGH CAPACITY ROADS

INDICATOR: Access time to a motorway or dual carriageway

PERIOD: 2021

SOURCE: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to access the nearest motorway or dual carriageway.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the longer it takes for businesses in the municipality to access a high-capacity road, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 47 municipalities initially lack this data: 44 are located on islands that do not have motorways or highways and the remaining 3 are exclaves. In the case of Llivia, as it is an exclave that can be accessed by land, the value relative to the nearest municipality (Puigcerdà) has been taken and the approximate distance between the two municipalities has been added. In the rest of the cases, the impossibility of accessing a high-capacity road is interpreted as something very negative, so the maximum value of the distribution has been imputed.

VALUE 70: ≥ 35.5 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 17.8 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 50. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.1 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 3.2: TRANSPORT AND STORAGE

INDICATOR: Access time to a company offering transport and/or warehousing services

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España); Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes it takes to reach the nearest municipality where a transport and/or warehousing company is registered.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the further away the companies of the municipality are from this type of services, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 10.4 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 5.2 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 51. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.2 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 3.3: DISTANCE TO AN URBAN MUNICIPALITY

INDICATOR: Access time to an urban municipality

PERIOD: 2022

SOURCE: Eurostat; Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

DESCRIPTION: It measures the approximate average time in minutes taken to reach the nearest urban municipality.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Inverse; the further away companies of the municipality are from a city, the less attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≥ 98.7 minutes

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 49.4 minutes

VALUE 130: 0 minutes

Figure 52. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.3 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 3.4: INTERNET COVERAGE

INDICATOR: Percentage of population with an internet coverage of 100 mbps

PERIOD: 2020

SOURCE: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico

DESCRIPTION: It measures the percentage of inhabitants of the municipality that have internet access with a connection speed of at least 100 megabits per second.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more inhabitants of the municipality have access to a fast internet connection, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0%

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 37.5%

VALUE 130: $\geq 75\%$

Figure 53. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 3.4 of the index for economic activity

4.2.4. DIMENSION 4: BUSINESS DYNAMISM

VARIABLE 4.1: PRESENCE OF COMPANIES

INDICATOR: Number of enterprises registered in the municipality

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Base de datos de empresas de la Cámara de Comercio de España (Camerdata)

DESCRIPTION: Direct; the more companies located in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Directa; cuantas más empresas estén radicadas en el municipio, más atractivo será.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0 companies

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 502 companies

VALUE 130: $\geq 1,004$ companies

Figure 54. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.1 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 4.2: EVOLUTION OF THE NUMBER OF COMPANIES

INDICATOR: Average net growth rate of legal employing units

PERIOD: 2020-2022

SOURCE: Coyuntura demográfica de empresas (INE)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the average growth in the number of companies in the municipality over the period.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more the number of companies in the municipality has grown on average, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 1,346 municipalities had a zero growth rate in at least one of the 12 trimesters of the period because there were no companies in them, so two types of imputations have been made: the 528 municipalities with valid rates in any of the three-month periods have been imputed a rate of 0 in the trimestres without data, and the 818 municipalities in which there were no companies in the whole period have been assigned the minimum value of the distribution.

VALUE 70: ≤ -4.86

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): -1.62

VALUE 130: ≥ 1.62

Figure 55. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.2 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 4.3: ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION

INDICATOR: Shannon Economic Diversification Index

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España)

DESCRIPTION: It measures how diversified the economy of the municipality is in terms of the distribution of companies in the 88 divisions of the National Classification of Economic Activities (CNAE-2009).

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more diverse the activities of companies in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: ≤ 1.5

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 3.2

VALUE 130: ≥ 4.9

Figure 56. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.3 of the index for economic activity

VARIABLE 4.4: BUSINESS SERVICES

INDICATOR: Percentage of enterprises offering services to other businesses

PERIOD: 2023

SOURCE: Camerdata (Cámara de Comercio de España)

DESCRIPTION: It measures the proportion of businesses registered in the municipality that provide services to other businesses, such as accounting, consultancy, administration, advertising, etc. To determine which companies fall into this group, the corresponding CNAE-2009 codes have been considered.

RELATIONSHIP WITH TERRITORIAL ATTRACTIVENESS: Direct; the more business services there are in the municipality, the more attractive it will be.

MUNICIPALITIES WITH IMPUTED VALUES: 0

VALUE 70: 0%

VALUE 100 (AVERAGE): 8.3%

VALUE 130: $\geq 16.6\%$

Figure 57. Geographical distribution of scores for variable 4.4 of the index for economic activity

5. ATTRACTIVENESS INDICES FOR SPECIFIC TARGET GROUPS

In addition to the two indices presented, three specific indices have been developed for different population groups, which have been calculated by modifying the weights of the variables and dimensions of the index for the general population, taking into account the specific characteristics of each group (young people, families or the elderly). Thus, although the starting point in all three cases is the same, the municipalities' scores vary according to the needs and interests of each group. It should be noted that the input variables that were part of the general index are not included in the construction of these specific versions.

5.1. COMPOSITION

5.1.1. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR THE YOUTH

The attractiveness index for the young population consists of a total of 37 variables, distributed in the 7 dimensions originally considered. The characteristics that differentiate it from the index for the general population are the following:

- Greater weight is given to the communications dimension
- The dimensions of health services and environment are given less importance
- Educational variables linked to the first stages (nursery schools, pre-school and primary education, and compulsory secondary education) are excluded
- Time spent in a day centre is excluded from the general services dimension

5.1.2. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR FAMILIES

The attractiveness index for families is the one that shows the closest resemblance to the original index, as it is constructed on the basis of a total of 40 variables distributed among the 7 predefined dimensions. In any case, it should be noted that the elements that define this index compared to the rest are the following:

- Greater weight is given to the educational dimension
- The environmental dimension is given less importance
- Time spent in a day centre is excluded from the general services dimension

5.1.3. ATTRACTIVENESS INDEX FOR THE ELDERLY

The attractiveness index for the older population is the one that differs the most from the others due to the characteristics of the target population group. In this sense, the index is composed of only 29 variables, and it is the only one that works with six dimensions instead of seven. The features that define this index in comparison with the rest of the indices for the population are the following:

- Greater weight is given to the dimensions of general and health services
- The demographic, economic and environmental dimensions are given less importance
- The educational services dimension is excluded in its entirety
- Labour market variables (unemployment and seasonality) are excluded from the economic dimension
- Variables related to internet coverage and road transport (high capacity roads and petrol stations) are excluded from the communication dimension

5.2. WEIGHTINGS

The main factor that differentiates the three specific indices from each other is the weighting assigned in each case to each of the seven dimensions considered. As we have already mentioned, in each index some dimensions are given greater importance than others, and this translates operationally into a differentiation of weights in three levels: the most important dimensions are assigned a 3, and the least important ones a 1, leaving those at a medium level of importance with a 2. Furthermore, in the case of the index for the older population, where a dimension is excluded from the calculation directly, a weight of 0 is assigned. After this assignment according to levels of importance, the sum of the values is calculated and each weight is divided by this to obtain the weights out of 1 and thus facilitate aggregation. Table 1 summarises how these weights are distributed:

Table 1. Weightings of the dimensions in the specific attractiveness indices

	Youth	Families	Elderly
Demography	2	2	1
Economy	2	2	1
General services	2	2	3
Health services	1	2	3
Educational services	2	3	0
Communications	3	2	2
Environment	1	1	1
Total	13	14	11

At the variable level, no differentiation of weights has been made, but rather it has been decided to exclude from the calculation those variables that are not very relevant for each group. In such cases, a weight equivalent to 0 was added to the variables affected, so that their value would not be taken into account in the calculation of the dimensions to which they originally belonged. The rest of the variables, those that are maintained in each index, acquire the same weight as the rest of the variables of the same dimension, which is ultimately equivalent to an arithmetic average. A summary of the variables that make up each of the three specific indices can be found in Table 2:

Table 2. Composition of the specific attractiveness indices

1 DEMOGRAPHY	Youth	Families	Elderly
1.1 Population density			
1.2 Average age			
1.3 Presence of women			
1.4 Population growth			
1.5 Births			
1.6 Migratory dynamics			
1.7 New residents			

2 ECONOMY	Youth	Families	Elderly
2.1 Business presence	✓	✓	✓
2.2 Economic diversification	✓	✓	✓
2.3 Income	✓	✓	✓
2.4 Unemployment	✓	✓	✗
2.5 Temporariness	✓	✓	✗
3 GENERAL SERVICES	Youth	Families	Elderly
3.1 Bank office	✓	✓	✓
3.2 Post office	✓	✓	✓
3.3 Library	✓	✓	✓
3.4 Police station	✓	✓	✓
3.5 Bar	✓	✓	✓
3.6 Day care centre	✗	✗	✓
3.7 Entertainment	✓	✓	✓
3.8 Daily services	✓	✓	✓
4 HEALTH SERVICES	Youth	Families	Elderly
4.1 Pharmacy	✓	✓	✓
4.2 Health centre	✓	✓	✓
4.3 Hospital	✓	✓	✓
4.4 Emergency services	✓	✓	✓
5 EDUCATIONAL SERVICES	Youth	Families	Elderly
5.1 Childcare	✗	✓	✗
5.2 Pre-school and Primary Education	✗	✓	✗
5.3 Compulsory Secondary Education	✗	✓	✗
5.4 Baccalaureate and Vocational Tr.	✓	✓	✗

5.5	University Education			
5.6	Extracurricular activities			
5.7	Extracurricular training			
6	COMMUNICATIONS	Youth	Families	Elderly
6.1	Distance to the provincial capital			
6.2	Distance to a reference municipality			
6.3	High-capacity road			
6.4	Petrol station			
6.5	Railway station			
6.6	Taxi			
6.7	Internet coverage			
7	ENVIRONMENT	Youth	Families	Elderly
7.1	Relief			
7.2	Rainfall			
7.3	Temperature			

CONCLUSIONS

Following the exhaustive literature review presented in Deliverable 4.1, a series of multidimensional indicators have been developed with the aim of quantifying the level of attractiveness of Spanish territories: one aimed at the general population, another at businesses, and three others at specific sectors of the population (young people, families and the elderly).

The scarcity of data at the municipal level available for the 8131 Spanish municipalities is notable and has considerably restricted the number and nature of the variables that have been used to construct these indicators, but good results have finally been achieved after months of work. The constant revision of the indicators together with internal feedback (from the other project partners) and external feedback (from the advisory committee) has allowed the optimisation of the products.

REFERENCES

- Instituto Nacional de Estadística. (2020). *Análisis multidimensional*.
<https://www.ine.es/ss/Satellite?c=Page&pagename=ProductosYServicios%2FPYSLayout&cid=1259947314645&L=0>
- Mazziotta, M., & Pareto, A. (2016). Methods for constructing non-compensatory composite indices: A comparative study. *Forum for Social Economics*, 45(2–3), 213–229.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07360932.2014.996912>
- Mazziotta, M., & Pareto, A. (2018). Measuring Well-Being Over Time: The Adjusted Mazziotta–Pareto Index Versus Other Non-compensatory Indices. *Social Indicators Research*, 136(3), 967–976.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-017-1577-5>
- OECD. (2008). *Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators: Methodology and User Guide*.
https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/economics/handbook-on-constructing-composite-indicators-methodology-and-user-guide_9789264043466-en